

ANALYSIS ON OPPORTUNITIES AND CHALLENGES OF AI IN THE BANKING INDUSTRY

Kartheek Pamarthi

USA

ABSTRACT

The fundamental objective of this SLR was to locate, evaluate, and synthesise the available data regarding the advantages and disadvantages of AI in banking. A number of AI-related potential for the industry were highlighted in the SLR. Banking regulators are encouraging the adoption of AI through law and collaboration, and numerous fin-tech start-ups are providing AI solutions for the banking industry. Additional opportunities can be found in areas such as smart wallets, decision-making, problem-solving, customer happiness and loyalty, process automation (particularly with regard to repetitive tasks), cybersecurity, improvements to transactions, and the promotion of digital financial inclusion. To counteract current and future AI threats, however, the financial industry's most influential players must devise suitable responses. Our list of top AI concerns includes: job loss, user acceptance issues, privacy breaches, limited creativity and adaptability, stringent operational requirements, digital divide, access to high-quality data, alignment of AI with business strategies, and the emotional "human touch" that AI once provided. A lot of the current research, meanwhile, is descriptive and relies on secondary sources. To better understand the possibilities and threats posed by AI in the financial sector, further empirical research is required.

Keywords: Artificial Intelligence (AI), Banking Sector, Challenges.

Cite this Article: Kartheek Pamarthi, Analysis on Opportunities and Challenges of AI in the Banking Industry, International Journal of Artificial Intelligence and Data Science (IJADS), 1(2), 2024, pp. 10–23.

<https://iaeme.com/Home/issue/IJADS?Volume=1&Issue=2>

1. INTRODUCTION

The Indian banking sector is undergoing a dramatic transformation, and artificial intelligence (AI) is leading the charge as a technical guardian. New possibilities and problems have emerged as a result of the revolutionary age that has just been ushered in by the integration of sophisticated AI technology with conventional banking procedures [1]. A tidal wave of new technologies has swept across the banking sector, shaking up several long-established models.

Factors such as 24/7 availability, financial integration, self-service machines, and internet banking have changed people's views on the importance of digital banking [2]. Artificial intelligence (AI) is playing a crucial role in changing the way banking services are provided and used in India, a country with a large population, varied economy, and quickly expanding tech industry [3, 4]. A plethora of elements influencing the modern financial scene underscore the necessity of institutions adopting AI. The enormous amount and complexity of financial data that banks process every day is one of the main factors [5]. It is impossible to handle the complexities of contemporary financial transactions, risk evaluation, and fraud detection using conventional data analysis approaches [6]. When it comes to navigating the complexities of the digital financial sector, artificial intelligence (AI) is becoming a vital tool due to its capacity to detect patterns, anomalies, and trends in large datasets [7]. Artificial intelligence (AI) is quickly becoming an essential component of banking operations, driven by the need to stay ahead of the increasingly fierce global competition. Faster decision-making, lower operating expenses, and regulatory compliance are three ways in which banks that use AI successfully gain an advantage over their competitors [8]. Banking operations are made more resilient and reliable with the addition of AI-driven automation, which further reduces the likelihood of human error [9]. Banks must immediately implement AI systems due to security issues. Modern cyber dangers require sophisticated and ever-changing security protocols [10]. Banks can protect their customers' sensitive financial information and keep up with ever-changing threats with the help of AI-driven cyber security systems that detect threats in real-time [11].

Artificial intelligence (AI) is changing the banking industry by making it more efficient, accurate, and adaptable [12]. Banks can now optimize their decision-making processes and evaluate massive datasets in real-time with the help of AI tools like natural language processing and machine learning algorithms [13]. Banks are able to provide their customers with more tailored and quick responses because to this cutting-edge intelligence, which also simplifies operational operations. The banking industry is rapidly undergoing a digital revolution, being propelled by the anticipation of clients for streamlined, technologically adept services [14].

Chatbots, virtual assistants, and predictive analytics are just a few examples of the new solutions made possible by AI, which is crucial in satisfying these expectations. In this age where the user experience is king, these apps do more than just improve interactions with customers; they also help retain and attract new ones. With the inevitable rise of digital transformation, the Indian banking sector is seeing the integration of AI as a need, not a luxury. With its wide-ranging effects on everything from security to client interactions, AI is set to be a game-changer for the future of banking in India [15]. Along with improving banks' operating capacities, the mutually beneficial interaction between technological innovation and financial services also encourages a resilient and adaptable market [16].

The ever-evolving world of finance has been profoundly impacted by the rise of artificial intelligence. Banking is being transformed as a result. We delve into the intriguing subject of "How Does AI in Banking Industry Impact the Future?" in this blog. As we delve into the realm where technology, finance, and other related concepts meet.

AI goes beyond being a mere cliché. This innovative technology is changing the way banks operate. Artificial intelligence (AI) simplifies processes, which improves efficiency and makes banking easier.

Come explore the myriad ways in which AI is influencing the future of banking with us. Here we'll delve into the ways chatbots are changing customer service, how AI and ML are influencing banking algorithms' risk management strategies, and what data-driven decisions mean for the future.

What is AI in Banking Industry?

Applying AI technologies like neural networks, data analytics, and natural language processing to automate and improve various parts of financial services is what is known as artificial intelligence (AI) in banking. It includes things like optimizing operational procedures, using chatbots for customer care, using AI to detect fraud in banking, evaluating credit, providing tailored financial advice, and more.

By analyzing massive amounts of data and making decisions based on that data, AI may help banks become more efficient, save money, and provide better customer experiences.

Thanks to its ability to detect suspicious activity and possible dangers in real time, this technology is an invaluable asset to contemporary banking institutions in their pursuit of compliance and security. Therefore, you should talk to a mobile banking app development firm if you want to put money into banking apps that use AI.

AI in Banking Market Statistics

Fig 1: AI in Banking Market Statistics

The AI in Banking Market Statistics is shown in figure 1.

- One-third of people who took the survey said their company has completely adopted AI. From \$6.82Billion in 2022 to \$9.00Billion in 2023, the worldwide AI market for banking is anticipated to expand at a CAGR of 32.1%.

- By 2030, the Asia-Pacific region will have generated about \$99 billion through the usage of AI in banking.

Following that, with 60% and 58% of the vote, predictive analytics and virtual assistants were deemed the runner-up innovations, respectively. In 2022, sales in North America will surpass 37% of total sales.

The new retail banking system that Bank of Georgia introduced in 2019 is powered by artificial intelligence.

How AI Is Transforming the Banking Sector?

There are very few distinguishing features across institutions in a well-developed market. Due to AI, this race is now completely open. Financial institutions can greatly benefit from artificial intelligence (AI) in the areas of competitive advantage, product attractiveness, and client acquisition. A significant majority of respondents (77%) said that banks' capacity to fully utilize AI was crucial to their long-term viability [17]. Optimization of storage, cloud infrastructure, and security can help banks improve their strategy. Customer experience is enhanced by the implementation of artificial intelligence, especially with large-scale language models. As an example, Deutsche Bank uses a banking app development company to integrate AI into their app. This helps consumers with portfolio management by giving them valuable advice based on risk indicators.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

It has already been said that AI is better and faster than humans at recognizing patterns. In certain patterns, these automated systems can spot irregularities that could indicate fraud. The fact that AI is ever-evolving and can tell the difference between real and fake content is also a plus. The number of transactions that are mistakenly marked as fraudulent is high. These erroneously identified fraudulent transactions can be eradicated by AI learning. Machines powered by artificial intelligence also aid in keeping tabs on transactions around the clock. Now that an AI system can do it, a person isn't even needed to check on charges at 3 in the morning. Because of this, there is a better chance that fraud will be identified and dealt with promptly [18].

In order to prevent fraud on the ever-growing digital banking channels, AI employs biometrics like iris and fingerprint scanners to confirm the user's identification. This aids in limiting who can access private data. Falsely detected transactions are one concern with AI in fraud protection. Even while AI is getting better, they still cause problems for businesses and their customers. Once again, AI fails to meet expectations in these instances. Do you think it will always be effective? This is not fraudulent, so why is it being marked as such? There is no easy way to address these questions, but they are ones that individuals might have. Machine Learning Assisting Buyers There are several ways in which AI might benefit consumers. AI chatbots are a great tool for providing efficient online customer service. They mimic human conversational abilities and offer instantaneous support for customer problems. The convenience of having inquiries addressed 24/7 by AI robots complements the work of human employees. In addition to increasing consumer involvement, AI can help them respond more fluently in more languages and keep their cool under pressure [19].

By tracking the customer's actions and interactions, AI may tailor their experiences to make them feel more personalized. A company's bottom line benefits from satisfied consumers and increased revenues.

The main problem with AI in this area is its inability to relate to and comprehend the customer's situation. The AI chatbot will continue with the standard procedure in the event that a customer phones the bank in a distressed and anxious tone, reporting the loss of their credit card. People need other people to respond with the right amount of compassion when they're feeling overwhelmed and anxious.

The market for artificial intelligence in financial technology was estimated to reach \$9.45 billion in 2021 and is projected to expand from 2022 to 2030, according to the Market Analysis Report. [20]. sing AI as a future-proof technology is a waste of time. This is not going anywhere; it has arrived. organizations like Google, Intel, Microsoft, and Oracle have been lauded for their contributions to AI's growth, but the technology is also making its way into smaller organizations and startups. Predicting the future, detecting fraud, and assisting with customer care are just a few ways in which AI will keep revolutionizing the FinTech business. Some are curious in the potential uses of generative AI in the financial sector. In the next years, generative AI may cause a sea change in the banking sector. It has the potential to automate a lot of mundane jobs, make better decisions, and boost financial efficiency in general. Generative AI can, for instance, detect market sentiment by analyzing textual data such as news articles, social media posts, and the like. Automated conversational interfaces powered by generative AI can also assist customers with inquiries and provide details about various financial services and products. Notably, there are certain obstacles that generative AI presents, such as possible biases and ethical concerns. Responsible use of generative AI in the financial sector is of the utmost importance.

Financial Inclusion Issues with Financial Technology

The advancements made in financial technology may cause some groups to be left out of the field's advantages. Obtaining the necessary technologies for FinTech is fraught with difficulties. A number of factors can contribute to people being unable to access financial services, including "financial and digital illiteracy," "potential biases in algorithms," "a lack of trust," and "a lack of access to digital infrastructure" [21]. It can be difficult and costly to use technology and the Internet. Some people just can't seem to get their heads around modern technology. Algorithms may also contain prejudices. As a result, "Algorithms used by banks to predict credit card debt defaults typically favor wealthier white applicants" [22] and current FinTech algorithms aren't always fair. These programs are capable of sexism, racism, and economic discrimination. While financial technology (FinTech) has the potential to greatly benefit many, it also leaves many out in the cold since they lack the financial means to participate.

Data Privacy/Security in Financial Technology

Financial technology firms gather a plethora of sensitive data, including names, addresses, SSNs, bank account numbers, and potentially account-accessing biometric information. Cybercriminals view this data as "gold" and exploit it to launch attacks such as phishing, data breaches, ransomware, and malware on financial technology institutions. A cyberattack on the world's largest lender by assets, the Industrial and Commercial Bank of China (ICBC) [23] is a recent example. A ransomware attack crippled Treasuries trading on November 9, 2023, at the ICBC's U.S. financial services business. The infection was caused by the software known as LockBit 3.0. It gains access to a company when an employee clicks on a malicious link in an email and steals confidential information. LockBit 3.0 is stealthy and difficult to identify. Security researchers face this challenge.

From July 2022 through June 2023, LockBit was the most common ransomware strain, responsible for about 28% of all ransomware assaults. As a company, LockBit uses the "ransomware-as-a-service" concept. Other hackers purchase its harmful software and use it to launch cyberattacks [24].

The US Department of Justice reports that LockBit perpetrators have carried out more than 1400 attacks globally and in the US, demanded ransom of more than \$100 million, and have received bitcoin payments totaling tens of millions of dollars. Ensuring client safety and operational security might pose a difficulty for these companies. Furthermore, data security becomes more challenging in an environment where several technologies, including various software and hardware kinds, are in use on a global scale. An uncoordinated environment makes it difficult to develop a strategy to combat cyberattacks, since every country has its own set of rules and regulations. People are hesitant to use FinTech for a variety of reasons, including worries about data privacy and security. Having faith that your data is secure in such settings can be challenging [25]. Having encryption, multifactor authentication, and firewalls in place is crucial to safeguard client data. It is crucial to encrypt text into ciphertext before transmitting it in order to prevent unauthorized parties from reading it. Because it requires more than just a login and password to access data, multifactor identification can aid in data security and privacy protection. This means that access to sensitive data is subject to a more stringent security procedure. Finally, firewalls should be installed by all FinTech organizations to monitor network traffic. They can use this information to prevent and detect malicious actions.

3. AI IN BANKING: OPPORTUNITIES AND CHALLENGES

Despite annual investments in the billions of dollars going toward banking technology's digital transformation, very few financial institutions have succeeded in integrating and expanding their use of artificial intelligence (AI). Issues plaguing current IT models and legacy technologies include disjointed data assets, poor communication and cooperation amongst business, customer, and tech teams, and an absence of an integrated AI strategy. In addition, the COVID-19 epidemic has sped up digital engagement, triggered seismic changes in consumer behavior, and skyrocketed expectations. As a means of creating unique value propositions and consumer experiences, established banks are transforming into AI-first and AI-driven companies. Artificial intelligence (AI) might provide banks an additional \$1 trillion per year in value, says McKinsey. Technologies using artificial intelligence are fundamental to the modern world. They have a reputation for being one of the most valuable companies in the world. Figure 2 shows AI and analytics for global banking.

Fig 2: AI and analytics for global banking

Research Dive assessed the worldwide digital market size for 2020 at USD 947.3 million in their Global Opportunity Analysis and Industry Forecast. But right now, the number is 972.2 million USD. Non-tech-savvy customers reduced branch visits and embraced internet banking as the COVID-19 epidemic impacted banking operations worldwide. More and more people are using digital banking, and with that comes the expectation that banks will adapt and provide smooth experiences. The digital transformation of the banking industry can be sped up by implementing AI systems.

AI Catalyzes the Digital Banking Landscape

When it comes to operations, customer support, marketing, risk management, and compliance, among other areas, banks are utilizing AI to its full potential for a comprehensive transformation. Artificial intelligence (AI) has the ability to make conventional processes more adaptable, future-proof, and scalable. Intelligent, tailored, timely, and relevant offerings and customer experiences are what AI-first banks are giving. In order to provide customers with appropriate services and products outside of banking, it is providing a consistent experience based on a deep understanding of their past behavior.

In order to enhance backend processes and provide personalized customer assistance, industry leaders are implementing innovative technologies like cognitive RPA, interactive voice response, pattern recognition, AI-based self-service apps, smart chatbots, biometric fraud detectors, and data mining tools. These algorithmic solutions outperform humans in terms of accuracy and productivity, which in turn increases revenue creation and decreases costs.

How will the AI-first Banks of the Future Look?

The majority of artificial intelligence (AI) initiatives in the banking industry are client- and demand-driven. According to a poll by Accenture, 71% of banking clients would rather have computer-generated customer service, which is in line with their constantly changing needs. However, when asked about automatic investing support, 78% of people said they would utilize it. Emerging trends in AI-first institutions are expected to encompass:

Asset Management: Using current events as a basis, AI-based advisors can provide recommendations. Both for risk modeling and for predicting how such occurrences may affect asset prices, they are valuable tools.

Credit Scoring: Artificial intelligence (AI) credit scoring provides a detailed analysis of data to speed up precise decisions. To examine data for score predictions with ease of scaling and reevaluation, AI systems use techniques like ensemble learning and machine learning (ML).

Fraud Detection: One of the most important components of a first-rate anti-money-laundering system is sophisticated pattern-matching analytics, which aid banking systems in detecting fraudulent activity. While cutting costs and decreasing the likelihood of unscrupulous activities, ML screens all transactions legitimately.

Market Research: To organize and categorize research materials, AI-powered smart agents employ natural language processing. Through the analysis of website terms, research reports, and financial market news, they provide strategic trade information and trends to bankers.

Customer Support: Cognitive ML is used by chatbots and AI assistants to detect emotions and context in customer service conversations. They are able to provide instantaneous responses to client inquiries and tailor-make financial recommendations because to natural language processing (NLP). Banks may save money and improve the digital client experience via self-help customer service.

4. AI APPLICATIONS IN BANKING

We have compiled a list of the five greatest AI banking apps suggested by a company that offers mobile app development services, while there are more excellent options available. Alright, let's check it out:

Table 1: AI banking apps

AI Banking Apps	Available Platforms	Download	Ratings
Chime	Android iOS	10M+	4.8
M1 Finance	Android iOS	1M+	4.5
Ally	Android iOS	1M+	3.5
Simple	Android iOS	1M+	3.1
Qapital	Android iOS	500k+	4.4

1. Chime:

Chime is an AI-driven Neobank that focuses on helping people maintain healthy financial lives through a variety of banking products and services. Using artificial intelligence, the software tracks users' purchases and provides them with financial information.

With round-up saving, a banking app like Chime will put any extra change that is not immediately spent into an investment or savings account.

2. M1 Finance:

M1 Finance is an AI-powered robo-advisor that streamlines financial planning processes. A user's risk tolerance and financial objectives might inform the creation and management of their portfolio.

With the use of smart algorithms, this top mobile banking software can automatically rebalance investment portfolios so that asset allocations are maintained. The program also has a feature called Smart Transfers that may be used to invest extra income automatically.

3. Ally:

Ally Bank created its AI-powered virtual assistant, Ally, to enhance customer connection. Natural Language Processing (NLP) is utilized by this software to comprehend and respond to user inquiries.

The platform allows users to access financial data, conduct transactions, ask inquiries, and receive personalized replies. The use of AI in the financial sector facilitates a more natural and effortless app navigation experience for consumers.

4. Simple:

Using artificial intelligence, Simple can study consumers' buying habits and deliver them tailored recommendations. By streamlining the processes of saving, budgeting, and achieving financial objectives, AI in investment banking helps customers maximize their finances.

On the other hand, you can use AI to build a simple app and grow your business. The capacity of AI to improve financial wellbeing is demonstrated by Simple's ability to learn users' behavior and deliver tailored recommendations.

5. Qapital:

Introducing Qapital, the AI-powered savings app. In order to assist users in saving money more efficiently, artificial intelligence and behavioral sciences are utilized. Users are able to choose their own savings objectives and regulations with Qapital. As an example, it can automatically keep any spare change and round up your daily transactions to the nearest dollar. Additionally, it may assess your spending patterns and provide recommendations for more effective cost-cutting measures. Hiring skilled mobile app developers is essential if you wish to create an app similar to Qapital.

Challenges in Adopting AI in Banking Industry

Also Fig 3: **Challenges in Adopting AI in Banking Industry** Is shown in figure. There will be difficulties associated with the widespread use of cutting-edge technology like AI. From security issues to a dearth of trustworthy data, generative AI presents a number of obstacles for the banking industry's technological users.

Fig 3: Challenges in Adopting AI in Banking Industry

Let's look at some of them now.

- **Data Security**

The banking industry must ensure that the data it collects is sufficiently protected to prevent breaches or infractions. Consequently, to safeguard your customers' data, you should seek out a technology partner with expertise in artificial intelligence (AI), banking, and a range of security measures.

- **Lack of Quality Data**

Organizations must utilize structured and top-notch data for training and validation before using AI solutions. They must employ high-quality data to guarantee the algorithm can handle real-world problems.

If your company is having problems with data that isn't machine-readable or organized, you really must employ AI developers. By ensuring data is processed correctly and in accordance with privacy policies, these specialists help to reduce dangers associated with AI model behavior and speed up the adoption of AI technologies.

- **Lack of Explainability**

Decisions can be made more efficiently and with fewer mistakes with AI-based solutions.

On the other hand, they could develop prejudices due to their history of bad decisions.

The reputation of the bank may be jeopardized if even small discrepancies in the AI system were to swiftly become widespread problems.

For every recommendation or judgment made by an AI model, banks should give a suitable amount of explanation. Doing so will aid in the prevention of disasters. It is imperative that financial institutions comprehend, verify, and justify the AI models' judgments.

Benefits of AI in Banking Industry

Significant gains have already been realized by banks following the implementation of AI in both their back-end and customer-facing operations. They consist of:

- **Better decision-making:**

Banking professionals, investment managers, and others in the financial sector can benefit from insights enabled by artificial intelligence. In the face of uncertain market conditions, they employ AI to reduce risks and maximize opportunities.

- **Personalized Customer Experiences:**

Customers are no longer subjected to generic product solicitations or lengthy wait times for assistance. Faster service and personalized information are provided to them through all digital channels, including websites, apps, and more.

- **Improved Efficiency:**

With the help of AI, banks can scale their operations and do away with the human errors that slow down manual procedures. Automating labor- and resource-intensive processes is the goal of AI development services systems. In turn, this enables the bank's employees to better serve their clients.

- **More Robust Security:**

Financial organizations can better safeguard their consumers' data with the help of AI. At the same time, AI enables banks to react quickly to cyber threats. Without delay, it detects and halts any fraudulent activity.

- **Improved Risk Management:**

AI enhances risk management by sifting through mountains of financial data. Bankers employ predicted insights to guide themselves through obstacles and seize market opportunities rather than making hasty decisions to safeguard assets.

- **AI-assisted Regulatory Compliance:**

Compliance with regulatory regulations, aided by AI: Banks assess their dedication to meeting regulatory obligations on an ongoing basis. The work that bank officers used to do is now automated by AI technologies. Institutions can save money and stay out of hot water using this.

- **Improved Privacy:**

AI enhances the sense of security and comfort for clients. By requesting the deletion of all conversational data, customers can choose not to provide any personal information.

5. USES OF AI IN BANKING INDUSTRY

1. Personalized Customer Experiences

Virtual assistants and AI chatbots have completely altered the banking industry's client-bank interaction. These intelligent systems use natural language processing to understand customer questions and provide personalized assistance around the clock. Banks can benefit from AI-powered personalized product and service recommendations by studying client data and past actions. Both the customer's happiness and the chances of cross-selling are enhanced by this. Businesses frequently team up with specialist entities, like a Chatbot app development company, to build sophisticated and customized solutions for their specific requirements, allowing for robust deployments.

2. Fraud Detection and Prevention

Artificial intelligence systems can instantly sift through mountains of transaction data in search of signs of fraud. Banks can swiftly identify suspicious activity with the help of machine learning algorithms that can learn from previous fraud trends. By identifying suspicious activity and alerting banks to potential fraud or illegal access, AI-powered fraud detection in financial systems can save customers' money. They safeguard the bank and its clients simultaneously.

3. Credit Risk Assessment

Manual procedures were used for determining creditworthiness in the past. By evaluating many types of data, including social media, AI and machine learning have made this process much easier. Banks are now able to make more educated lending choices more quickly thanks to these models developed by a machine learning app development company. 4. Trading by Algorithms Algorithms powered by artificial intelligence have changed the way banks trade. Algorithms like this analyze AI trends and execute trades far faster and more accurately than human traders employing historical data, news, and market data could ever hope to do. The use of AI in trading systems has the potential to increase returns by better managing portfolios and risks.

4. Robotic Process Automation

Automating repetitive actions based on rules is a key component of RPA bots in banking operations. Tasks including data entry, reconciliation, and report preparation are automated by these robots. Employees can focus on higher-level, more valuable jobs because of this. As a result, expenses are cut and mistakes are reduced. It results in increased precision and conformity as well.

5. Predictive Analytics for Customer Insights

Data-driven AI-powered predictive analytics can foretell a consumer's tastes and actions. Banks can use this data to tailor product suggestions and run more precise marketing campaigns. In order to increase customer retention and happiness, banks must first understand their customers' demands. Profitability is driven by this in the end.

6. Regulatory Compliance and Anti-Money Laundering

Meeting the ever-increasing regulatory standards is a continual struggle for banks. Artificial intelligence (AI) is crucial for audit efficiency because it can search through transaction data for suspicious patterns that could indicate fraud or money laundering. Banks can save time and money with these technologies, and they also help with compliance by reducing false-positives.

Future of AI in Banking Industry

Almost every market is being affected by digital technology. This has far-reaching effects on both the industry and company management. In today's technologically advanced world, every industry is exploring and executing new possibilities.

The expansion of the banking sector is being propelled by digitalization, which is a worldwide occurrence. Now the dilemma is, how can banks help more people without charging them more?

When consumers' demands change, businesses have to change with them. Modern consumers have lofty standards. Customers nowadays are tech-savvy and want businesses to make their experiences enjoyable and hassle-free. The financial industry is likewise expected to meet their expectations.

Mobile banking, real-time money transfers, and e-banking are just a few examples of how the banking industry has expanded its reach into retail, IT, and telecom to better serve its customers. These cutting-edge features put banking in the hands of consumers, but they come at a cost to the financial system.

The involvement of information technology, retail, and telecom increases the likelihood of confidential information being sent over virtual networks. Occasionally, it might cause financial institutions to fall victim to cyberattacks or fraud. Both the bank's bottom line and customers' faith are impacted by this form of fraud. One major use of AI in banking is to provide customers more relevant recommendations based on their priorities. Customer satisfaction with bank services is improved with the use of artificial intelligence. The bank gains a better grasp of customer expectations with the use of AI, or artificial intelligence.

CONCLUSION

AI is going to completely change the way banks operate very soon. Its effects will be far-reaching, improving efficiency, security, and customer experiences. Banks can mitigate risk and deliver individualized service with the use of AI-powered personalized services, fraud detection, and predictive analytics. The future of banking is bright, with the prospect of new ideas, easier processes, and a renewed emphasis on customers' wants and requirements. A new age of banking, characterized by cutting-edge technology and a focus on the consumer, is about to dawn. But by teaming up with an AI app development company, banks and other financial institutions can tap into AI's full potential and provide customers with innovative services and tailored experiences.

REFERENCES

- [1] Easwaran, B.; Aramuthakannan, S.; Lokesh, S.; Kumar, R.; Saikia, K.J.; Saikia, U. A study on the use of data science in healthcare applications and the mathematical issues in data science. *J. Algebr. Stat.* 2022, 13, 2535–2541. [Google Scholar]
- [2] Chakravaram, V.; Vidya Sagar Rao, G.; Jangirala, S.; Sunitha, R. The role of big data, data science and data analytics in financial engineering. In *Proceedings of the International Conference on Big Data Engineering*, Hong Kong, China, 11–13 June 2019; pp. 44–50. [Google Scholar]
- [3] Özsu, M.T. Data science—A systematic treatment. *Commun. ACM* 2023, 66, 106–116. [Google Scholar] [CrossRef]
- [4] Cao, L. Data science: Challenges and directions. *Commun. ACM* 2017, 60, 59–68. [Google Scholar] [CrossRef]
- [5] Cao, L. AI in finance: Challenges, techniques, and opportunities. *ACM Comput. Surv.* 2022, 55, 1–38. [Google Scholar]
- [6] TensorFlow. TensorFlow Case Studies. 2023. Available online: <https://www.tensorflow.org/about/case-studies> (accessed on 20 November 2023).
- [7] NLTK. Natural Language Toolkit. 2023. Available online: <https://www.nltk.org/> (accessed on 20 November 2023).

- [8] IBM. What Is Data Science? 2023. Available online: <https://www.ibm.com/topics/data-science> (accessed on 20 November 2023).
- [9] Apache. The Apache Hadoop Software Library. 2023. Available online: <https://hadoop.apache.org/> (accessed on 20 November 2023).
- [10] Barbaglia, L.; Consoli, S.; Manzan, S.; Recupero, D.R.; Saisana, M.; Pezzoli, L.T. Data science technologies in economics and finance: A gentle walk-in. In *Data Science for Economics and Finance: Methodologies and Applications*; Consoli, S., Recupero, D.R., Saisana, M., Eds.; Springer: Cham, Switzerland, 2021. [Google Scholar]
- [11] Pisoni, G.; Molnár, B.; Tarcsi, Á. Data science for finance: Best-suited methods and enterprise architectures. *Appl. Syst. Innov.* 2021, 4, 69. [Google Scholar] [CrossRef]
- [12] TransUnion. Fraudsters Shift Focus at Mid-Point of 2021 from Financial Services to Travel and Leisure and Other Industries. 2021. Available online: <https://newsroom.transunion.com/fraudsters-shift-focus-at-mid-point-of-2021-from-financial-services--to-travel-and-leisure-and-other-industries/> (accessed on 20 November 2023).
- [13] Das, S.R. The future of fintech. *Financ. Manag.* 2019, 48, 981–1007. [Google Scholar] [CrossRef]
- [14] Hendershott, T.; Zhang, X.; Zhao, J.L.; Zheng, Z. Fintech as a game changer: Overview of research frontiers. *Inf. Syst. Res.* 2021, 32, 1–17. [Google Scholar] [CrossRef]
- [15] Grand View Research. Artificial Intelligence in Fintech Market Size Report. 2023. Available online: <https://www.grandviewresearch.com/industry-analysis/artificial-intelligence-in-fintech-market-report> (accessed on 20 November 2023).
- [16] Tok, Y.W.; Heng, D. Fintech: Financial Inclusion or Exclusion. 2022. Available online: <https://www.imf.org/en/Publications/WP/Issues/2022/05/06/Fintech-Financial-Inclusion-or-Exclusion-517619> (accessed on 20 November 2023).
- [17] Kharpal, A. China's ICBC, the World's Biggest Bank, Hit by Cyberattack that Reportedly Disrupted Treasury Markets. *The New York Times*. 2023. Available online: <https://www.cnbc.com/2023/11/10/icbc-the-worlds-biggest-bank-hit-by-ransomware-cyberattack.html> (accessed on 20 November 2023).
- [18] Treleaven, P.; Galas, M.; Lalchand, V. Algorithmic trading review. *Commun. ACM* 2013, 56, 76–85. [Google Scholar] [CrossRef]
- [19] Mukerji, P.; Chung, C.; Walsh, T.; Xiong, B. The impact of algorithmic trading in a simulated asset market. *J. Risk Financ. Manag.* 2019, 12, 68. [Google Scholar] [CrossRef]
- [20] Hilbert, M.; Darmon, D. How complexity and uncertainty grew with algorithmic trading. *Entropy* 2020, 22, 499. [Google Scholar] [CrossRef] [PubMed]

- [21] Duhigg, C. Traders Profit with Computers Set at High Speed. The New York Times. 2009. Available online: <https://www.nytimes.com/2009/07/24/business/24trading.html> (accessed on 20 November 2023).
- [22] Pardoe, I. Autoregressive Models. 2023. Available online: <https://online.stat.psu.edu/stat501/book/export/html/996> (accessed on 20 November 2023).
- [23] IMARC. Algorithmic Trading Market Research Report. 2023. Available online: <https://www.imarcgroup.com/algorithmic-trading-market> (accessed on 20 November 2023).
- [24] Manne, K. Not So Fast, Robots: Humans Are Still the Best Stock Traders. 2023. Available online: <https://www.buffalo.edu/news/news-releases.host.html/content/shared/mgt/news/not-so-fast-robots-humans-still-best-stock-traders.detail.html> (accessed on 20 November 2023).
- [25] Koshiyama, A.; Firoozye, N.; Treleaven, P. Algorithms in future capital markets: A survey on AI, ML and associated algorithms in capital markets. In Proceedings of the First ACM International Conference on AI in Finance (ICAI), New York, NY, USA, 15–16 October 2020; pp. 1–8

Citation: Kartheek Pamarthi, Analysis on Opportunities and Challenges of AI in the Banking Industry, International Journal of Artificial Intelligence and Data Science (IJADS), 1(2), 2024, pp. 10–23

Abstract Link:

https://iaeme.com/Home/article_id/IJADS_01_02_002

Article Link:

https://iaeme.com/MasterAdmin/Journal_uploads/IJADS/VOLUME_1_ISSUE_2/IJADS_01_02_002.pdf

Copyright: © 2024 Authors. This is an open-access article distributed under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution License, which permits unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided the original author and source are credited.

This work is licensed under a **Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International License (CC BY 4.0)**.

✉ editor@iaeme.com